

Studies of the Tartrate Complexes of Magnesium, Strontium and Barium

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The stability constants of the tartrate complexes of Magnesium, Strontium and Barium have been determined by the *pH* titration method. The equilibrium constants of the reactions $Mg^{++} + T^{-} \rightleftharpoons MgT$, $Sr^{++} + T^{-} \rightleftharpoons SrT$ and $Ba^{++} + T^{-} \rightleftharpoons BaT$ are found to be 81.197, 1.79×10^3 and 1.56×10^3 respectively at 37°.

Cannan and Kibirick¹ determined the stability constants of the tartrate of magnesium, strontium and barium to be 22.91, 44.67 and 41.69 respectively. Joseph² found the stability constants of strontium and barium tartrates by e.m.f. determination methods to be 87.10 and 89.13 respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Barium perchlorate solution (M/20) was prepared in a manner similar to the preparation of calcium perchlorate solution mentioned in tartrate complex of calcium².

Results of *pH* titrations performed for the investigations are tabulated in table I.

TABLE I

Expt.	Temp.	Volume of solution titrated.	Contents of solution titrated.	Titrant	Results.
I	A 37°C	120 ml	Tartaric Acid :- 0.01 gm. mole NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole	M/2 NaOH	Fig. I Curve A
	B-do	-do	Tartaric Acid :- 0.01 gm. mole NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole MgSO ₄ :- 0.001 gm. mole	-do-	Fig. I Curve B
II	A 37°C	100 ml	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole	M/10 Sodium Tartrate,	Fig. II Curve A
	B -do-	-do-	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole MgSO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole	-do-	Fig. II Curve B
III	A 37.5°C	120 ml	Tartaric Acid :- 0.01 gm. mole NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole	M/2 NaOH	Fig. III Curve A
	B -do-	-do-	Tartaric Acid :- 0.01 gm. mole NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole Sr (NO ₃) ₂ :- 0.001 gm. mole	-do-	Fig. III Curve B

1. Cannan and Kibirick, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2914.

2. Joseph, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1946, **164**, 529.

TABLE I (contd.)

Expt.	Temp.	Volume of solution titrated.	Contents of solution titrated	Titrant	Results
IV	A 37.5°C	100 ml	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole	M/10 Sodium Tartrate	Fig. IV Curve A
	B -do-	-do-	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole Sr (NO ₃) ₂ :- 0.001 gm. mole	-do-	Fig. IV Curve B
V	A 37°C	120 ml	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole Tartaric Acid :- 0.01 gm. mole	M/2 NaOH	Fig. V Curve A
	B -do-	-do-	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole Tartaric Acid :- 0.01 gm. mole Ba (ClO ₄) ₂ :- 0.001 gm. mole	-do-	Fig. V Curve B
VI	A 37°C	100 ml	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole	M/10 Sodium Tartrate	Fig. VI Curve A
	B -do-	-do-	NaClO ₄ :- 0.01 gm. mole Ba (ClO ₄) ₂ :- 0.001 gm. mole	-do-	Fig. VI Curve B

DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained in the experiments are similar to those obtained during the investigation of calcium tartrate.³

In experiments I, III and V the ratio of metal to ligand is 1:10. The horizontal distance between the two curves indicates the amount of total tartrate ligand bound

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

due to the formation of the complex. It can be shown as before in case of calcium tartrate complex that

$$\bar{n} = \frac{[T]_x - [T]_y}{[\text{Metal Salt}]}$$

where x and y are two points on the same pH axis and $[T]_x$, $[T]_y$, $[\text{Metal Salt}]$, $\bar{n}$ represent the total tartrate at x and y, the concentration of metal salts i.e., MgSO_4 , $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ba}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ at y and the number of tartrate ligands bound per metal ion respectively.

The values of $\bar{n}$ calculated for magnesium tartrate complex are found to be 0.1054, 0.0893, 0.0680, 0.06656, 0.06709, 0.05147 and 0.04913 at pH values 3.25, 3.325, 3.55, 3.75, 4.025, 4.10 and 4.45 respectively.

The values of $\bar{n}$ for strontium tartrate complex determined are 0.2150, 0.1956, 0.1932, 0.1878, 0.1650 and 0.1030 at pH values 3.58, 3.76, 4.00, 4.20, 4.35 and 4.70 respectively.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

The n values for barium tartrate complex are found to be 0.1738, 0.1709, 0.1677 and 0.1530 at pH values 3.79, 3.92, 4.24 and 4.42 respectively.

The n values never exceeded unity and hence the formation of 1:1 complex is indicated.

In case of curve B of figures II, IV and VI the pH rises in the beginning, the rise being very slow after the addition of very nearly one gm. mole of sodium tartrate per gm. atom of the metal salt. This also indicates the formation of a 1:1 complex.

The lower pH of system B is mainly due to the removal of tartrate ion from the solution by the metal ions due to the complex formation.

The reactions in experiments II, IV and VI are represented by the equation (1) and the equilibrium constants by equation (1-1)

and

$$\frac{[MT]}{[M^{++}][T^{--}]} = K \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

where $[M^{++}]$, $[T^{--}]$ and $[MT]$ represent the molar concentrations of the metal ion, free tartrate ion and the complex respectively.

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

It can be shown as in case of calcium tartrate complex that

$$[T^{--}] = [T]_A$$

$$[MT] = [T]_B - [T]_A$$

and $[M^{++}] = [\text{Metal Salt}] - [MT]$

where A and B are two points on the same pH axis.

TABLE II

pH	$[T]_A \times 10^3$	$[T]_B \times 10^3$	$[\text{MgSO}_4] \times 10^3$	$[\text{MgT}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Mg}^{++}] \times 10^3$	$K \times 10^{-1}$
6.775	3.555	5.661	9.434	2.106	7.328	6.08
6.800	3.796	6.103	9.391	2.307	7.084	8.22
6.825	4.030	6.542	9.346	2.512	6.834	9.12
6.850	4.580	6.977	9.303	2.397	6.906	7.58
6.870	4.898	7.408	9.259	2.510	6.749	7.59

TABLE III

pH	$[T]_A \times 10^3$	$[T]_B \times 10^3$	$[\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \times 10^3$	$[\text{SrT}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Sr}^{++}] \times 10^3$	$K \times 10^{-2}$
6.67	1.186	2.913	1.146	1.727	9.733	1.496
6.70	1.380	3.383	1.140	2.003	9.397	1.544
6.73	1.575	3.847	1.134	2.272	9.068	1.591
6.78	1.818	4.762	1.124	2.944	8.296	1.952
6.80	1.961	5.214	1.119	3.253	7.937	2.089
6.825	2.152	5.661	1.114	3.509	7.631	2.137

TABLE IV

pH	$[T]_A \times 10^3$	$[T]_B \times 10^3$	$[\text{Ba}(\text{ClO}_4)_2] \times 10^3$	$[\text{BaT}] \times 10^3$	$\text{Ba}^{++} \times 10^3$	$K \times 10^{-2}$
6.85	2.274	4.762	1.095	2.488	8.462	1.293
6.87	2.439	5.214	1.090	2.775	8.125	1.401
6.89	2.629	5.661	1.085	2.992	7.858	1.448
6.90	2.724	6.103	1.080	3.379	7.421	1.671
6.91	2.913	6.542	1.075	3.629	7.121	1.750
6.93	3.100	6.977	1.068	3.877	6.803	1.839

The values for $[T]_A$, $[T]_B$, $[\text{MgSO}_4]$, $[\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Ba}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$, $[\text{MgT}]$, $[\text{SrT}]$, $[\text{BaT}]$, $[T^{--}]$, $[\text{Mg}^{++}]$, $[\text{Sr}^{++}]$ and $[\text{Ba}^{++}]$ were calculated as in case of calcium tartrate and are tabulated in tables II, III, and IV for magnesium, strontium and barium respectively. The values of K for magnesium, strontium and barium tartrate complexes are found to be 81.19, 1.79×10^2 and 1.56×10^2 respectively.